

1 **Observation and Analysis of Anomalous Terrestrial**
2 **Diffraction as a Mechanism of Electromagnetic**
3 **Precursors of Earthquakes**

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6 **Key Points:**

- 7 • A low-noise high-sensitivity technique is proposed to observe anomalous radio
8 wave signals associated with earthquakes.
9 • Possible electromagnetic precursors of earthquakes have been detected by ob-
10 servation networks placed near major tectonic lines.
11 • Large-scale numerical analysis has suggested that anomalous diffraction is the
12 mechanism of the electromagnetic precursors.

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13 **Abstract**

14 Detection of earthquake precursors has long been a controversial issue with regard
 15 to its possibility and realizability. Here we present the detection of electromagnetic
 16 anomalous signals before large earthquakes using an observation network of very
 17 high frequency (VHF) radio wave receivers close to major tectonic lines in Japan.
 18 The receivers are equipped with specifically designed narrowband filters to sup-
 19 press noises and to detect extremely weak signals. We detected different types of
 20 electromagnetic anomalies before earthquakes around mountainous and coastal re-
 21 gions, where presence of electric charges is anticipated on the surface located in the
 22 middle of the radio wave paths near major tectonic lines in Japan. We use numer-
 23 ical electromagnetic wave analysis to show that when electric charges are present
 24 on a ground surface as a consequence of tectonic activity, the surface charges in-
 25 teract strongly with radio waves and eventually cause strong diffraction of the ra-
 26 dio waves. The analysis was performed using the three-dimensional finite-difference
 27 time-domain (3D-FDTD) method with digital elevation models of the actual geo-
 28 graphical landforms on a massively parallel supercomputer. The results confirm the
 29 consistent mechanisms of the electromagnetic precursors, which explains the anoma-
 30 lous electromagnetic signals observed by the authors before large earthquakes.

31 **1 Introduction**

32 Electromagnetic signals could be enhanced and received at distant locations
 33 some days or weeks before earthquakes. Researchers have tried to observe such elec-
 34 tromagnetic anomalies and precursors associated with earthquakes for more than 20
 35 years (Kushida & Kushida, 1998, 2002; Fujiwara et al., 2004; Moriya et al., 2005;
 36 Hayakawa et al., 2007; Uyeda et al., 2009; Moriya et al., 2009, 2010; Freund, 2011;
 37 Yasuda et al., 2009; Bleier et al., 2013). The observation of such anomalies has been
 38 difficult and unstable because they are affected by geographical, atmospheric, iono-
 39 spheric conditions and disturbed by environmental noise of random nature. Various
 40 possible electromagnetic precursors have been so far reported and a number of hy-
 41 potheses have been proposed: i.e., ionospheric perturbation by Kushida et al. (Kushida
 42 & Kushida, 1998, 2002) and Hayakawa et al. (Hayakawa et al., 2007; Yasuda et al.,
 43 2009; Bleier et al., 2013), lithosphere-atmosphere-ionosphere (LAI) coupling by Pilipenko
 44 et al. (Pilipenko et al., 2001), atmospheric anomalies (Fujiwara et al., 2004), a bulk
 45 plasmon model (Kamogawa & Ohtsuki, 1999), and chemical models (Enomoto &
 46 Hashimoto, 1990; Enomoto et al., 1997). All of these models are inclusively possible,
 47 not exclusively, but difficult to explain the anomalous radio wave phenomena com-
 48 prehensively, especially in the very high frequency (VHF) band.

49 On the other hand, the mechanism of the anomalous radiowave propagation
 50 has been explained reasonably by the theory of the ground surface plasma wave ap-
 51 pearing on the surface of the Earth (Fujii, 2013, 2016). It has been experimentally
 52 shown that positive electric charge carriers come out from the peroxy bond in ox-
 53 idized minerals when rocks are subjected to tectonic deviatoric stresses (Freund,
 54 2000, 2002, 2011; Bleier et al., 2013), and that such carriers can even move across
 55 the composite boundary of rocks along crustal faults. Although it is still contro-
 56 versial, this fact could explain the possible presence of electrostatic charges on the
 57 Earth's surface associated with co-seismic or pre-seismic activities. Another possibil-
 58 ity is the change of ground resistivity with earthquakes (Rikitake & Yamazaki, 1978)
 59 even at a distance of 1,000 km from epicenters, which could be supported by the the-
 60 ory that the size of the precursor deformation zone of earthquakes is estimated by a
 61 simple formula as a function of its magnitude (Dobrovolsky et al., 1979). Therefore,
 62 electric charges on the ground surface must play a role in seismic activity. In gen-
 63 eral, if electric charges exist on a surface, then the charges are subjected to the force
 64 by the external oscillating electric field. This is equivalent to the well-known surface

65 plasmon in optics induced by light on metal surfaces (Kittel, 1986; Raether, 1977,
66 1988; Fujii, 2014).

67 In this paper, we present our observation results of anomalous radio wave sig-
68 nals that strongly depend on the polarization and the propagation path of the wave.
69 We then analyze the propagation of the radio waves and show a possible mechanism
70 of the anomalous propagation and diffraction caused by an interaction between the
71 radio wave and the surface electric charges, which can be referred to as the terres-
72 trial surface plasmon. This paper does not deal with the fundamental mechanism of
73 the earthquake itself, but rather focuses on the possible electromagnetic phenomena
74 on the Earth's surface with electric charges associated with earthquakes. The anal-
75 ysis was performed using the three-dimensional finite-difference time-domain (3D-
76 FDTD) method (Yee, 1966; Taflove, 1995) with the properties of the mobile elec-
77 tric charge carriers of the Drude dispersion model (Taflove & Hagness, 2005; Fujii,
78 2013, 2016). The analysis method and the computational code have been verified by
79 comparison with the theoretical solutions of localized surface plasmons on a metal
80 sphere (Fujii, 2014). Several analyses have been carried out with different landforms
81 of irregular shapes in mountainous regions and coasts to show that the electromag-
82 netic interactions occur randomly and depend strongly on the topography of the
83 ground surface. The numerical results agree well with the observed polarized radio
84 wave signals.

2 Radio Wave Observation Geometry and Equipment

We observe radio waves from distant broadcast stations as shown in Figure 1 and in Table 1. Since these radio signals are significantly weak, we have developed highly sensitive low-noise measurement systems that employ super-narrow-band filters for significant noise reduction implemented over a network of distant observation sites (Fujii, 2023a).

Figure 1. The map of broadcast and observation stations focused in this study as listed in Table 1 and the epicenter of the $M7.4$ Fukushima offshore earthquake (E141° 37'22", N37° 41'48", depth 57 km) on Mar. 16, 2022 at 23:36:32.6 (JST) on the Pacific side of Japan. The symbols of the black circle and the square are for the broadcast and observation stations, respectively. White arrows indicate the radio wave paths, and the yellow circular regions indicate the possible points of causing anomalous diffraction, which are Mt. Okuhotakadake, Atsumi Peninsula, and Itoigawa, analyzed in the following sections. Thin black lines are the Median Tectonic Line and the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line. Tokyo and Kyoto are shown for reference. The earthquakes in the Kamikochi/Okuhotakadake region discussed later and listed in Table 2 occurred in the limited area within approximately 10 km distance of the black triangle near the center of the map.

2.1 Noise Reduction by Super-Narrow-band Notch Filter and Observation System

The radio wave observation system is composed of standard Yagi antennas of 3 to 6 elements in horizontal and/or vertical polarization depending on the allowable facility as summarized in Table 1, and digital radio receivers AOR AR5001D and/or AR2300, which are controlled by PCs. The radio wave is measured every 10 s at the Toyama and Yatsuo stations, and every 20 s at the Iwata station. For stable detec-

Table 1. List of the radio broadcast and observation sites focused in this paper. The polarization and the number of elements of the Yagi antennas at the observation sites are shown in parentheses with the form of (Polarization, Number of elements). Polarization notations H and V are for horizontal and vertical linear polarizations, respectively. Height is that of antenna comprised of altitude above sea level and approximate height of antenna facility. 80.9 MHz is an unused frequency in Japan and is monitored for comparison as discussed in the text.

Observation sites:						
Site Name	(Pol., Elem.)	Longitude	Latitude	Height (m)		
For Toyama/Yatsuo:						
Toyama City, Toyama Pref.	(H,5) (V,6)	E137° 11'13"	N36° 41'38"	30		
Yatsuo, Toyama City, Toyama Pref.	(H,3)	E137° 07'51"	N36° 37'10"	30		
For Iwata:						
Iwata City, Shizuoka Pref.	(H,5)	E137° 49'20"	N34° 39'20"	4		
Broadcast sites:						
Freq.(MHz)	Power	Site Name	Pol.	Longitude	Latitude	Height (m)
For Toyama/Yatsuo:						
80.9	0 W	(no broadcast)	—	—	—	—
82.3	1 kW	Niigata	H	E138° 48'30"	N37° 42'24"	600
88.3	100W	Iida	H	E137° 52'21"	N35° 27'33"	771
For Iwata:						
78.9	3 kW	Tsu	H	E136° 26'01"	N34° 43'57"	320
79.2	1 kW	Shizuoka	H	E138° 27'56"	N34° 58'27"	300
80.9	0 W	(no broadcast)	—	—	—	—

98 tion of earthquake precursors, effective noise reduction in the measurement system is
 99 essential. Super-narrow-band notch (band-rejection) filters (Fujii, 2021) are inserted
 100 between the antenna and the receiver to reduce unwanted intense radio waves from
 101 nearby broadcast stations by more than 20 dB from a typical -50 dBm signal level
 102 down to -70 dBm, etc., allowing clear uninterrupted observation even in urban ar-
 103 eas as described in the following. Note that dBm is a unit of electric power in dB
 104 relative to 1 mW reference power.

105 The frequency characteristics of the super-narrow-band notch filter used for
 106 the Toyama observation station are shown in Figure 2 (a). The filter attenuates
 107 the radio wave signals from nearby stations by -25 dB each, and the rejection band-
 108 width is as narrow as approximately 1 MHz. Since the target signal from the Niigata
 109 broadcast station at 82.3 MHz is very close to the unwanted signal at 82.7 MHz, the
 110 target signal is also attenuated by approximately -11 dB; this may unwillingly de-
 111 grade the necessary radio wave power. However, the third-order intermodulation
 112 caused in the amplifying circuit of most receivers would have worse effects, which
 113 has been reduced by the filters by more than -30 dB. This results in the reduction
 114 of the noise floor under -90 dBm to -100 dBm as shown in Figure 2 (b).

115 Note that 80.9 MHz is a frequency that is not used for broadcasting in Japan;
 116 it is monitored in this study to see if broadband noise is observed simultaneously
 117 with anomalous signals at different frequencies (Yoshida et al., 2006). The effect of
 118 the filter is clearly seen when the filter was removed occasionally for maintenance on
 119 March 9, 2022, from 12:00 to 17:00, and the noise floor increased by 30 dB to 40 dB
 120 depending on the frequency due to the nonlinear intermodulation effect. The reduc-
 121 tion of the third-order intermodulation noise is therefore considered critical and has
 122 a higher priority than the slight loss of necessary signals; otherwise, the precursors
 123 are weak and hidden behind the noise. Note also that different filters and receiver
 124 are used for each observation system, even at the same site, depending on the di-
 125 rections of the target broadcast stations. The 88.3 MHz wave from Iida is observed
 126 with a different system than the 82.3 MHz wave from Niigata, and therefore it is not
 127 shown in Figure 2, whereas the noise reduction capability is in the same level.

128 The super-narrow-band notch filter consists of a series capacitor of several
 129 pico-farads and a high quality-factor (low-loss) inductance of approximately 1 nH.
 130 The inductance is formed by a short-circuited low-loss 12D-FB coaxial cable of 60 cm
 131 to 70 cm length, determined according to the frequency to be rejected, and has a
 132 quality-factor of 25 to 30 at the VHF band. The circuit is shown in Figure 2 (c) for
 133 one unit structure; for its use in actual observation, a necessary number of the unit
 134 structures are cascaded as shown in Figure 2 (d). It should be noted that commer-
 135 cially available inductors are mostly not applicable due to their much higher losses
 136 and lower quality factors.

137 The notch filters are used in all observation systems to attenuate unwanted
 138 radio wave signals and reduce the noise floor; thus, it is not necessary to go to an
 139 unpopulated district in search of an electromagnetically quiet environment for ob-
 140 servation. In addition, the coaxial cables connecting the antennas and receivers are
 141 loaded with numerous ferrite cores to reduce the common-mode noise. The target
 142 broadcast stations were chosen in such a way that their radio signals were signifi-
 143 cantly weak but close to the limit of detection. The system was first operated for a
 144 certain period of time to search for radio waves that carry anomalies under critical
 145 propagation conditions.

Figure 2. An example of the super-narrow-band notch filter implemented in one of the observation systems in Toyama. (a) Frequency characteristics of the whole filter. Blue dotted lines show the frequencies to be rejected i.e., 77.7 MHz, 81.5 MHz, 82.7 MHz, and 90.2 MHz for the Toyama station (TYM), and the orange and red solid lines show the target frequencies to be observed at 80.9 MHz and 82.3 MHz, respectively. (88.3 MHz wave from Iida is observed by another system and is therefore not shown here.) (b) Noise reduction effect of the filter; the filter was removed for occasional maintenance on March 9th from 12:00 to 17:00, i.e., for the period of the high-level state of the step, otherwise the filter was inserted. The height of the step is, therefore, the level of the achieved noise reduction. "H" refers to the antenna polarization as horizontal. (c) Unit circuit of the notch filter. (d) The appearance of the whole filter. A total of 8 units are cascaded to reject 4 frequencies. The coaxial cables are rolled to fit in a 25 cm-wide, 30 cm-long, and 10 cm-high box.

3 Observed Anomalous Radio Signals before Earthquakes and Numerical Analysis

In this paper, we show first some of the anomalous signals that we observed by the above-mentioned system. In order to clarify the physical mechanism of the anomalous radio wave propagation that is possibly related to earthquakes, we have performed large-scale electromagnetic analyses using the FDTD method on a massively-parallel supercomputer with digital elevation models of the landforms. We have analyzed the effect of landforms such as mountains, valleys, and coasts, with and without electric charge carriers on the propagation of electromagnetic waves in air and on surfaces (Fujii, 2013, 2016, 2023b, 2024c). The computational resources used for the analyses were 64 nodes, 2304 CPU cores, 3 to 5 TB of memory, and the wall time of 5 to 20 hours per job on a Cray CS400 supercomputer.

3.1 Mountainous Region of Japan Alps

In the region of Japan Alps, we had a series of earthquakes larger than $M5$ in April - May, 2020, as listed in Table 2, near the Okuhotakadake peak ($E137^\circ 38'53''$, $N36^\circ 17'20''$, height 3189.5 m), referred also to as Kamikochi region shown near the center of Figure 1. Since approximately a year before the earthquakes, we observed a series of anomalous signals; in the normal state, the signal level was below -100 dBm, but suddenly it increased by about 20 dB and lasted for several hours or even longer and returned to the previous signal level; they look like rectangular pulses with different periods and heights, as shown by the arrows in Figure 3. A single rectangular pulse signal was observed on December 30, 2016, as shown in Figure 3 (a), which may be due to the possibility that the preparation phase of the earthquakes continues intermittently, as earthquakes occur periodically in this particular region, including the group of small events in 2018; the origin of this single anomaly has not yet been identified.

Similar phenomena of such pulse anomalies have also been observed regarding the pre-seismic radio wave propagation, and its statistical analysis was presented for earthquakes in a mountainous area in Hokkaido, Japan (Moriya et al., 2010). In the case of our observations, an association with earthquakes can also be inferred. In Figure 3(a), the times of the earthquakes are indicated by the stars. Interestingly, these anomalous signals appear mostly in the vertical polarization (upper plots) and not in the horizontal polarization (lower plots), while the polarization of the broadcast radio wave is horizontal, which is difficult to explain by artificial noise and can be presumed to be a natural phenomenon. More detailed anomalous signals for this case are shown in Supporting Information (Fujii, 2024c) Section 3.1 Figures 27 to 29.

From these facts, it is presumed that the radio wave from Iida is diffracted by the high peaks of the Japan Alps and then reaches the observation station in Toyama. This propagation path is obviously out of sight due to the high mountains in this region. However, it is an interesting problem how radio waves propagate when electric charges appear on the surface of the mountain peaks, which has been studied by the numerical analysis in the following.

3.1.1 Numerical Analysis Conditions

As shown in Figure 4, the size of the analysis region is chosen to be 860 m from west to east, 710 m from south to north including the peak point at the origin of the analysis region, and an altitude higher than 3070 m up to 3240 m i.e., 170 m in height. The peak of the mountain has an altitude of 3189.5 m, and the gap between the peak and the upper boundary of the analysis region is approximately 50 m. The original digital elevation model (DEM) grid has a resolution of about 5m, and finer

Figure 3. (a) Observed radio wave power in dBm for the wave propagation from Iida to Toyama at 88.3MHz since 2017 till 2022 obtained by the authors; time data for the whole observation period are plotted to show their long-term perspective. For more detailed signals, see (b) and (c), and their descriptions below. Arrows indicate the time of occurrence of the anomalous rectangular-shaped pulse signals. Large black stars indicate the time of the major earthquakes in Kamikochi district ranging from $M5$ to $M5.5$ (JMA); some of which occurred in a particular short period are listed in Table. 2. Small black stars show those of smaller earthquakes of $M4.3$ to $M4.8$ in the same district. A medium white star shows a group of 49 small earthquakes of $M1.9$ to $M3.1$ in the same district during the short period from November 23 to November 30, 2018. After these major events, anomalous rectangular-shaped signals are rarely seen, except for short ones lasting less than a few minutes. (b) Example of the observed signals expanded for 10 days from May 6 to May 16, 2019. (c) Another example of the period of 10 days from Dec. 2 to Dec. 12, 2019. The anomalous rectangular-shaped pulses with sudden increase in their power levels are pointed by the arrows in (b) and (c). For each sub-figure, the upper plot is the vertical polarization data and the lower plot is the horizontal polarization data. The anomalous rectangular signals are mostly observed for the vertical polarization. The data for the horizontal polarization exhibit some spike noises and those possibly caused by sporadic E layers in ionosphere, and some very weak rectangular anomalies are seen at the same time as those for the vertical polarization.

Table 2. List of the major earthquakes in the Kamikochi/Okuhotakadake district discussed in this section. They occurred in a limited area of approximately 10 km distance near the center of Figure 1 (black triangle), and within a time period of about a month. Magnitude M is of JMA. The maximum seismic intensity of Japan scale (Max SI) is also shown.

No.	Epicenter (Longi. Lati.)	M	Date	Time (JST)	depth	Max SI
1	Nagano middle part E137° 39'42" N 36° 13'30"	5.5	April 23, 2020	13:44:22.1	3 km	4
2	Nagano middle part E137° 39'00" N 36° 14'06"	5.0	April 23, 2020	13:57:55.1	5 km	3
3	Nagano middle part E137° 38'12" N 36° 15'06"	5.0	April 26, 2020	02:22:49.4	6 km	3
4	Gifu Hida District E137° 37'42" N 36° 17'00"	5.4	May 19, 2020	13:12:58.1	7 km	4
5	Nagano middle part E137° 38'24" N 36° 15'42"	5.3	May 29, 2020	19:05:14.9	4 km	4

195 grids of 0.2 m resolution were obtained by spline interpolation for the FDTD anal-
 196 ysis. The boundaries of the analysis region were all set to be the perfectly matched
 197 layer (PML) absorbing boundary of 50 layers and the reflection from the boundary
 198 was minimized. For the whole mountain model, the relative dielectric permittivity
 199 was set to $\epsilon_\infty = 6$ and the electric conductivity $\sigma = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ S/m. The parameters
 200 of the Drude dispersion are plasma frequency $f'_p = 408$ MHz and damping frequency
 201 $\Gamma = 2\pi \times 10^7$ rad/s for the electrically charged ground (Fujii, 2016). The incident
 202 wave has horizontal polarization of the E_z component, same as the real radio broad-
 203 cast, and the frequency is set to be 70 MHz i.e. the wavelength is 4.3 m in air. The
 204 incident wave is entered in the x -direction from south to north so that it hits the
 205 peak of the mountain.

206 3.1.2 Numerical Results

207 The analysis results are shown in Figure 5. To distinguish the behavior of ra-
 208 dio waves for the cases with and without the surface charges, it is easily recognizable
 209 to plot only the vertical component E_y . The vertical cross-section of the landform
 210 on which the radio wave field will be plotted is shown in Figure 5(a). In these plots,
 211 the incident wave is not included; only the scattered or diffracted wave in the verti-
 212 cal polarization is observed. In the case where no earthquake is expected and there
 213 is no surface electric charge, the radio wave is diffracted at the peak as a normal
 214 phenomenon and the wave partially penetrates the ground as shown in Figure 5(b).
 215 In contrast, for the case where crusts are stressed and electric surface charges appear
 216 on the peak, the radio wave is strongly scattered and diffracted in random directions
 217 as shown in Figure 5(c); this is considered to be the anomalous mountain diffraction
 218 caused by the peak covered with surface electric charges.

Figure 4. 3D model of the Okuhotakadake peak of 3189.5 m altitude. The origin of the horizontal axes is collocated with the peak. Altitude h is taken in the y -direction. The digital elevation model (DEM) is publicized by the Geographical Survey Institute, Japan.

Figure 5. FDTD analysis results of the vertical component $|E_y|$ for the Okuhotakadake peak on the vertical plane from the south to the north that includes the peak point. The incident wave is of horizontal E_z polarization. Altitude h is taken in the y -direction. (a) Vertical landform on the plane of the field plot, (b) without surface charge, and (c) with surface charge.

219 In Figure 6, similar effects are clearly observed in the horizontal plane at 3120 m.
 220 These results clearly show that the radio wave strongly interacts with the surface
 221 electric charges; the strong field along the surface is considered to be the surface
 222 plasma wave or the surface plasmon and they are induced around the peak and prop-
 223 agate downward along the surface. They are partly scattered by surface roughness
 224 and re-radiate the radio waves, which are diffracted again by the next lower peaks.
 225 Interestingly, the radio wave is scattered toward various random directions in a beam-
 226 like form as clearly seen in Figure 6(c) compared to (b). This randomness in the
 227 scattering and diffraction would cause the randomness in the ability to detect the
 228 anomalous signals at particular observation locations, i.e., anomalies are detectable
 229 in some locations, but not in others, literally randomly, as the electric charges on the
 230 ground surface vary according to the stress to the crusts. The beam-like diffraction
 231 is a general phenomenon that is commonly seen in most of our analyses; this could
 232 be a possible mechanism for an anti-symmetric behavior of the observation results in
 233 Toyama and in Yatsuo, as discussed in the next section.

234 It is of particular importance to evaluate the quantitative agreement between
 235 the observation and the numerical analysis. We assume the typical environmental
 236 conditions for a broadcast radio wave with its source power $P_0 = 1$ kW, and it is ob-
 237 served at a distance of $r = 100$ km. Then, the intensity (magnitude of the pointing
 238 vector or the power flow per unit area) of the radio wave is estimated over a tenta-
 239 tive sphere surface of radius r as $p = P_0/4\pi r^2 \approx 8 \times 10^{-9}$ W/m². In the numer-
 240 ical analysis, the electric field strength of the incident wave is set to approximately
 241 1 V/m, and that of the diffracted radio wave is typically 1% to 5% of the incident
 242 wave that is found in Figures 5 and 6. If we assume that it is 1%, then the inten-
 243 sity of the diffracted wave will be $p = 8 \times 10^{-9} \times 0.01^2 = 8 \times 10^{-13}$ W/m² =
 244 8×10^{-10} mW/m² (milli-watts per square meter). We also assume that the effective
 245 antenna cross section for the Yagi antenna is of the order of $a = 1$ m², then, the re-
 246 ceived power for the Yagi antenna is estimated to be $P = ap = 8 \times 10^{-10}$ mW, which
 247 is $10 \log_{10} P \approx -90$ dBm; this value is the receivable power when the anomalous
 248 diffraction occurs, and is consistent with the received power for the observed anoma-
 249 lous signals, typically -90 dBm to -100 dBm as found in all the observation results
 250 such as Figure 3, and Figure 7 in the later section.

Figure 6. FDTD analysis results of vertical component $|E_y|$ for the Okuhotakadake peak on the horizontal plane at an altitude of 3120 m, which is 69.5 m down from the peak. The incident wave is of horizontal E_z polarization incoming from the south. (a) Configuration of the landform on the plane of the field plot, (b) without surface charge, and (c) with surface charge.

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3.2 Pacific Coast of Central Japan

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Next, we consider the anomalous radio wave propagation in the coastal regions. As shown in Figure 7, one day before the Fukushima earthquake of $M7.4$ on March 16, 2022, we detected significantly clear radio wave signals of possible earthquake precursors at two locations over 200 km apart (Fujii, 2023a). For this event, the anomalous signal at the Iwata observation station from the Tsu broadcast station (fourth slot from above) was much larger than those at the Toyama (first slot) and Yatsuo (second slot) stations, leading to the implication of earthquakes occurring near the Pacific side rather than the Japan Sea (north) side. Eventually, about 15 hours after the maximum of the anomalous signal, the Fukushima offshore earthquake occurred. The epicenter for this event is shown in Figure 1. The anomalous signal from the Shizuoka broadcast station to the Iwata observation station (third slot in Figure 7) also exhibits moderate variation, which could be due to the influence of the nearby Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line. More examples of the anomalous signals are found in Supporting Information (Fujii, 2024c) Sections 4.2.3 and 4.2.5.

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It is very interesting to note that the variation of the anomalous signals for Toyama (first slot) and Yatsuo (second slot) shows an anti-symmetric behavior; when the signal increases in Toyama, the signal decreases in Yatsuo, and vice versa. Such phenomena in a small district of only 10 km distance is difficult to explain by meteorological or ionospheric phenomena such as radio ducting and sporadic E layers, but can be explained by anomalous diffraction due to surface electric charges as discussed in the previous section; more details are found in (Fujii, 2024c) Section 4.2.4.

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Note also that, in Figure 7, the observed signals show some smaller fluctuations even after the main shock (e.g. March 17, 2022, at 00:00 in the second slot, and same day at 8:00 in the fourth slot, also smaller fluctuations in other plots). These post-cursor signals are often seen in other cases as well, which can be attributed to the crustal activity in the associated nearby regions, and to the other smaller earthquakes. More examples are found in (Fujii, 2024c) Section 4.2.7. Although there are some uncertainties that are difficult to fully describe, the significance in this case is that the major anomalies occurred almost simultaneously. Long-term observation data are found again in (Fujii, 2024c) Section 4.2.6 and in Supporting Data Set-1 and 2 (Fujii, 2024a, 2024b) on the corresponding pages in chronological order. It is also noteworthy that during the period of the Fukushima $M7.4$ earthquake in Figure 7, 80.9 MHz signals did not show any particular variations either in Toyama, Yatsuo or in Iwata observation station, suggesting that no broadband noise was observed; for the observation data, see (Fujii, 2024c) Section 4.2.3 Figures 6 to 9, and related part.

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3.2.1 Numerical Analysis Conditions

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In the lower part of Figure 1, the landform near the radio wave path from Tsu to Iwata is shown by white arrows. Along this radio wave path, there are some landforms that can cause radio wave diffraction, such as high cliffs along the Pacific coast of Atsumi peninsula. The numerical model of the coast including the cliff of several ten meters in height is shown in Figure 8. The size of the analysis region is 1420 m from west to east, 600 m from south to north, including a part of the Pacific Ocean. The total height of the analysis region is 100 m; the height above sea level is 96 m, added with the tentative 2 m-deep sea water and 2 m-thick sea bottom, which have little effect on the analysis results.

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The relative dielectric permittivity was set to $\epsilon_\infty = 6$ and the electrical conductivity $\sigma = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ S/m for the ground, and $\epsilon_\infty = 80$, $\sigma = 4.0$ S/m for the seawater.

Figure 7. Comparison of the anomalous signals observed in Toyama, Yatsuo and Iwata around the Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ earthquake on March 16, 2022. Star symbol shows the time of the earthquake.

302 The parameters of the Drude dispersion are $f_p' = 408$ MHz and $\Gamma = 2\pi \times 10^7$ rad/s for
 303 the electrically charged ground as in the previous analysis. The seawater was treated
 304 as a normal lossy conductive medium. The grid size of the DEM is approximately
 305 5 m, and it was refined by the spline interpolation to obtain the FDTD grid of 0.2 m
 306 resolution. The analysis region is surrounded by 50 layers of perfectly matched layer
 307 (PML) absorbing boundaries and was analyzed with the 70 MHz incident radio wave
 308 from the west.

309 **3.2.2 Numerical Results**

310 In the analysis results, for the case where electric charges are present on the
 311 surface, it was found that polarization-dependent anomalous diffraction of radio
 312 waves can occur (Fujii, 2023b), which is shown in Figure 9; due to the complicated
 313 landform, the scattered and diffracted radio waves form many narrow beams and ra-
 314 diate in random directions, which is clearly seen in (c) compared to the result in (b).
 315 In particular, due to the high cliff that runs for long distance along the Pacific coast,
 316 it is presumed that horizontally polarized waves are scattered and diffracted, which
 317 are all superimposed, and the enhanced wave reaches the observation site. These re-
 318 sults suggest the physical mechanism of the anomalous radio wave signals caused by
 319 the interaction between the surface charges and radio waves.

Figure 8. The 3D analysis configuration of a south coastline of Atsumi Peninsula indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 9. FDTD analysis results of the coastline of Atsumi Peninsula on the horizontal plane at an altitude of 56 m above sea level. The incident wave is of horizontal E_x polarization radiated from the west, and horizontal E_z component is plotted. (a) Horizontal landform on the plane of the field plot, (b) Without surface charge, and (c) With surface charge.

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3.3 Japan Sea North Coast of Central Japan

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We also consider the radio wave propagation in the coastal region on the Japan-Sea side near the Itoigawa district in Figure 1, where anomalous signals are often observed. As shown in Figure 7, radio wave observation data for Toyama (first slot) and those for Yatsuo (second slot) have typical characteristics of anti-symmetric behavior and simultaneous fluctuation. For more examples, see Supporting Information (Fujii, 2024c) Section 4.2.3. These anomalies are difficult to explain by meteorological and ionospheric phenomena, whereas they can be explained by the anomalous diffraction at electrically charged ground surfaces.

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The radio wave path for this district is from Niigata to Toyama, which is approximately 180 km apart along a coastline and beyond the line of sight due to the curvature of the ocean surface. However, there is a landform of a steep mountain in the very vicinity of the Japan Sea, which is in the Itoigawa district that can cause diffraction of the radio wave by the cliff-like landform. Moreover, the radio wave path crosses the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line, along which the stress-induced electric charges may have a relatively high mobility and appear on the nearby ground.

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3.3.1 Numerical Analysis Conditions

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The mountainous landform has been extracted from the Itoigawa district as shown in Figure 10, and the propagation and diffraction of the radio wave have been analyzed for this region. The size of the analysis region was 650 m from west to east, 300 m from south to north. The height above sea level is 190 m, and below the sea level is tentatively set as 2 m-deep sea water and 2 m-thick sea bottom, which has only little effect on the analysis, so that the total height is 194 m.

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The material parameters are the same as in the previous section, $\epsilon_\infty = 6$, $\sigma = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ S/m for the ground, and $\epsilon_\infty = 80$, $\sigma = 4.0$ S/m for the seawater. The parameters of the Drude dispersion are $f'_p = 408$ MHz, and $\Gamma = 2\pi \times 10^6$ rad/s for the electrically charged ground. Seawater is always assumed to be a normal non-Drude lossy conductive medium. These are typical analysis conditions used for other cases of anomalous radio wave diffraction by landforms (Fujii, 2013, 2016, 2023b).

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The incident wave is chosen to be 70 MHz with the horizontally polarized E_x -component radiated from east to west, from the rectangular source region from $x = 30$ m to 270 m, and from $y = 112.4$ m to 180.3 m, which simulates the actual radio wave path from the broadcast station in Niigata City.

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3.3.2 Numerical Results

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This analysis region has a large steep mountainous landform, and the steep and rugged slopes are close to the sea, a part of which is shown on the horizontal cross section of the landform in Figure 11(a). Under normal conditions, the radio wave is blocked by the mountainous landform and only a very weak signal reaches the observation point. This is shown in Figure 11(b) and its expansion (c). However, when electric charges are present, the radio wave is diffracted along the slope and propagates around to reach the other side behind the mountain, which appears imperceptibly in Figure 11(d) because the diffracted wave has the same polarization as the incident wave and is dominated by much stronger incident field; the diffracted wave is clearer in the expanded plot in (e). This phenomenon of diffraction allows the horizontally polarized wave to reach the observation site in Toyama.

Figure 10. 3D analysis configuration of a coastline along the northern west sea (Japan Sea) side of Japan near Itoigawa City. Altitude h is in the y -direction. the original digital elevation model of approximately 5 m resolution publicized by the Geographical Survey Institute, Japan.

Figure 11. FDTD analysis results of the coastline along the Japan-Sea side of Japan on the horizontal plane at an altitude of 112.4 m above sea level. The incident wave is of horizontal E_x polarization radiated from the east, and the same horizontal E_x -component is plotted. (a) Configuration of the landform on the horizontal plane at an altitude of 112.4 m. (b) Without surface charge, the white rectangular part of the wave propagation is expanded in (c). (c) Without surface charge, the white rectangular part of (b) expanded. (d) With surface charge, the white rectangular part of the wave propagation is expanded in (e). (e) With surface charge, the white rectangular part of (d) expanded.

4 Discussions

We have observed some anomalous radio wave signals before medium and large earthquakes as shown in the previous sections of this paper and in the Supporting Information (Fujii, 2024c). For all the radio waves that show such anomalous signals, we have noticed some common properties regarding the path of the wave: (i) the distance of the radio wave path is slightly beyond the line of sight, and it is not too far and not too close, (ii) there is a possible diffraction point in the middle of the path, for which, if diffraction occurs, the radio wave can reach the observation site, (iii) there is also a major tectonic line nearby, and the radio wave crosses it over or propagates near it. Conversely, if the above conditions are not satisfied, anomalous signals will not appear or will appear only weakly. Therefore, it is reasonable to consider that the anomalous signals were observed as a variation from the normal state of mountain diffraction, which has been well-studied in the past (Barsis & Kirby, 1961).

The above properties are seen in Figure 1 and understood by the coordinates in Table 1; the approximate distances between the broadcast and observation stations are 150 km from Iida to Toyama, 130 km from Tsu to Iwata, and 180 km from Niigata to Toyama, all apparently beyond the line of sight of the radio wave due to the curvature of the Earth and/or the mountains in between. The distance from Shizuoka to Iwata is 68 km, which is relatively shorter than the other distances, but still beyond the line of sight due to the mountains, and the radio wave could be influenced by the nearby Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line. The electromagnetic field analyses have confirmed that when the electric charges appear on the ground surface, they interact with radio waves propagating near the ground, and that the interaction causes anomalous diffraction of the radio wave, as suggested also numerically and theoretically (Fujii, 2013, 2016), which supports the above common properties (i) to (iii). The behavior of the interaction varies depending on the landform, e.g., whether it is of mountain or coast.

In mountains, as the surface charges are induced and repel each other, moving toward the peak and accumulating there, the interaction with radio waves continues for a certain period of time depending on the amount of charges generated by the crustal activity. Anomalous signals thus form a rectangular-shaped pulses with a high potential state for the corresponding lifetime of the charges. This agrees with the similar pulse signals observed in the mountainous region in Hokkaido, Japan (Moriya et al., 2010). If the peak of the mountain has at least an area comparable to the wavelength of the radio wave, i.e. only a few meters, then it would act as an antenna and re-radiate waves of vertical polarization, i.e., basically perpendicular to the ground surface near the peak. This scenario is supported by our numerical results.

In contrast, along coasts, surface charges may flow away through the conductive part of the ground or through the seawater, rather than accumulating in one place like the case for a mountain peak. Then the lifetime of such surface charges would be shorter than that on the mountain peaks, and the electric charges would appear and disappear as quickly as they are generated by crustal activity. Thus, the anomalous signals may have a different time variation of the fluctuation compared to that of the rectangular pulses. As briefly mentioned in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, the typical landform of cliffs can cause the anomalous diffraction of the horizontally polarized wave, which is enhanced by the tens of kilometers of coastal landform and then reaches the observation site.

The time period of the possible precursors is years before the earthquakes for our case of the mountainous region of the Japan Alps, while it is only a few days for the case of the coasts of the Atsumi Peninsula and Itoigawa district. This differ-

417 ence is considered to be the difference in the phase of the earthquake; in the prepa-
 418 ration phase, which could be a long continuous process before the final failure of the
 419 crust, stress is applied to the crusts and elastic potential energy accumulates there;
 420 after such a period, immediately before the failure, there could be a foreshock stage,
 421 which also varies from a few tens of minutes to a few days, and we can observe a
 422 short-term precursor (Dobrovolsky et al., 1989). This scenario varies due to the dif-
 423 ference in the crustal properties of the epicentral regions and the rate of stress ac-
 424 cumulation on the crust. This will influence the temporal synchrony between the
 425 precursors and the occurrence of earthquakes, which can vary greatly depending on
 426 the crustal structure and the geology and geography where the precursors are ob-
 427 served. Therefore, the knowledge of the electrical or electromagnetic behavior of the
 428 particular site, obtained through long-term observations, would elucidate the typical
 429 causality between precursors and earthquakes.

430 5 Conclusions

431 Various possible electrical precursors have been detected by electromagnetic
 432 wave observation in the central part of Japan. Such anomalous phenomena are gen-
 433 erally subtle and vague. However, with our network observation systems and sophis-
 434 ticated noise reduction filters, stable detection of the anomalous signals has been
 435 realized. In this paper, the mechanism of the electromagnetic precursors has been
 436 proposed and verified by theoretical and numerical analyses of the electromagnetic
 437 wave propagation near the surface of the Earth.

438 We have considered the following particular ground surfaces where we observed
 439 possible electromagnetic precursors of earthquakes: (a) a peak of Mt. Okuhotakadake,
 440 close to an epicenter in Kamikochi district, (b) a coastline of the Atsumi Peninsula
 441 with random cliffs near the Median Tectonic Line, and (c) a coastline of Itoigawa
 442 with steep mountain slopes near the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line. From the
 443 extensive analysis of these landforms, it has been highly possible that the domi-
 444 nant mechanism of the electromagnetic precursors is the anomalous diffraction by
 445 charged ground surfaces; these landforms block the line-of-sight paths of the radio
 446 wave propagation, whereas the diffraction of the radio wave by the electric charges
 447 on the ground causes significant scattering and re-radiation of the radio wave, which
 448 can be detected as precursors at observation sites.

449 We have demonstrated the stable low-noise observation method, physical mech-
 450 anism, and numerical analysis of the electromagnetic precursors of earthquakes,
 451 which had been extremely controversial and difficult to clarify for a long time. Now,
 452 a highly feasible method for monitoring the underground crustal activity and detect-
 453 ing potential earthquake precursors are suggested in terms of where to locate the
 454 observation stations and which broadcast stations to choose; i.e., choose the trans-
 455 mitting and observing stations so that the radio wave path is only slightly beyond
 456 the line of sight and that the radio wave path crosses a major tectonic line or an
 457 expected epicentral zone. Conversely, without fulfilling these conditions, the detec-
 458 tion of earthquake precursors would be difficult. We propose the above guidelines
 459 to continue monitoring the underground crustal activity, and eventually clarify the
 460 correlation property between electromagnetic anomalies and earthquakes.

461 6 Open Research

462 Data of earthquakes from the searching service by the Japan Meteorological
 463 Agency (JMA) available at [https://www.data.jma.go.jp/svd/eqdb/data/shindo/
 464 index.html](https://www.data.jma.go.jp/svd/eqdb/data/shindo/index.html) (JMA-EQ, n.d.). Precipitation and temperature data from JMA at
 465 <https://www.data.jma.go.jp/obd/stats/etrn/> (JMA-Weather, n.d.). Ionograms
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467 wdc.nict.go.jp/cgi-bin/ionog/sum_control.cgi (NICT, n.d.). Geomagnetic
468 field data from JMA Kakioka Magnetic Observatory, 2013, Kakioka geomagnetic
469 field 1-minute digital data in IAGA-2002 format [dataset], Kakioka Magnetic Ob-
470 servatory Digital Data Service, doi:10.48682/186bd.3f000, available at [http://www](http://www.kakioka-jma.go.jp/obsdata/metadata)
471 [.kakioka-jma.go.jp/obsdata/metadata](http://www.kakioka-jma.go.jp/obsdata/metadata) (JMA-GM, n.d.).

472 Supporting Information, including detailed radio wave observation data, is
473 originally available in an institutional repository site at [http://www3.u-toyama.ac](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportInfo_20240704.pdf)
474 [.jp/densou01/SupportInfo_20240704.pdf](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportInfo_20240704.pdf), and also in the multiple resource repos-
475 itory site ZENODO for the findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)
476 capability (Fujii, 2024c).

477 Long-term radio wave data and various environmental data integrated into
478 time-synchronized comparison diagrams are originally available in an institutional
479 repository site at [http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet1_20240704](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet1_20240704.pdf)
480 [.pdf](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet1_20240704.pdf) and [http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet2_20240704](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet2_20240704.pdf)
481 [.pdf](http://www3.u-toyama.ac.jp/densou01/SupportDataSet2_20240704.pdf), and also in the multiple resource repository site ZENODO (Fujii, 2024a, 2024b).

482 Figures were made with Gnuplot version 5.2.8 available under Copyright by T.
483 Williams, and C. Kelley at <http://www.gnuplot.info> (Williams & Kelley, n.d.).

484 The map was created using the open-source software QGIS version 3.22.5,
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